

Effect of co-polymer on catalytic properties of POMs using one-pot synthesis of Biginelli reaction

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Abstract

Polyether amines belong to a class of green di-block copolymer of ethylene oxide and propylene oxide moieties with terminal amine functionality. These polymers are biocompatible and show temperature dependant phase separation properties. Modification of phosphotungstic acid (PTA) with polyether amine (Jeffamine[®]) (PTA-Jeffamine[®]) resulted in a solvent-less liquid-like material. Synthesis of the catalyst (PTA-Jeffamine[®]) is cost-effective and scalable due to easy availability of the individual components and nature of the synthesis protocol. One-pot synthesis of Biginelli reaction was performed in presence of PTA as catalyst and polyether amine (Jeffamine[®]) as additive. PTA-Jeffamine simultaneously catalyzes oxidation of benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde and nucleophilic addition of benzaldehyde, ethyl acetoacetate and urea to form 3, 4-dihydropyrimidinones. Biginelli compounds, 3,4-dihydro-2(1H)-pyrimidinones, are interesting compounds in the fields of therapeutics, synthesis, and bio-organic chemistry. Their derivatives exhibit a wide spectrum of biological effects. The products were characterized by UV-visible, FT-IR, ¹H, ¹³C NMR spectroscopy.

Key words: Polyether amines; catalyst; Biginelli reaction; NMR spectroscopy.